

RESEARCH ON NEEDS ANALYSIS REPORT OF THE STUDENTS OF UZBEK STATE WORLD LANGUAGES UNIVERSITY

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Annotation Gathering information about learners' needs are very essential part to design a good curriculum. As Kathleen Graves (2001) claims, a successful curriculum is intended to assess the needs of the learners. The process of analyzing learners' need helps to identify their desires, expectations and purposes and to formulate clear goals of curriculum. In addition, needs analysis can be applied to find out the challenges, which learners encounter during the learning process. In order to prepare this report, I observed the second - year students of Uzbekistan State World Languages University. The purposes of these efforts were to find out the capability of the students to meet the requirements of determined curriculum, to analyze what skills they need to improve.

Key words:Needs analysis, learner, UzSWLU, Methods, curriculum, learner profile, proficiency level, results, findings, learning skills, CEFR

Learner Profile

I monitored a group of 16 students, where 11 of them were female and 5 were male. Their ages were between 19 to 24 years, they also had different interests. Moreover, the academic performance of students significantly varied from each other. As to their cultural background, all of them were born in Uzbekistan and are Uzbek native speakers, while only 4 of them speak Russian as well. During my observation I also tried to closely monitor a student whose language proficiency level of English was higher comparing to the other students. The reason of choosing her was to determine why her performance was greater than others. It was a female of 24 years old, who has difficulties in writing essays, preparing drafts of official

letters as well as summarizing articles. However, her strength was in her habit of reading a lot of English books of different genres and levels. In personal informal interview with her it became clear that before entering this university she studied at English focused school and has been learning the language for 6 years.

Methodology

In order to analyze the class performance and abilities of the students, I preferred to employ different approaches and sources of information. As J.C.Richards advocates (2001) since one source of information considers incomplete, a triangular approach is better to analyze the learners' needs. Therefore, my analysis was prepared based on assessments of the student's progress in writing, the report of the teacher on students' challenges in education process, the personal interviews with a learner and the outcomes of the test and questionnaires given to the students. In this project the students agreed to participate in it after explaining them the purpose of work scope. All 16 students took part in the questionnaire and the test about learning style, but only 10 of them (the remaining were absent) took the test for the proficiency level of language. The consent form was signed by a student, who was interviewed besides the tests and questions and whose writing skills were assessed in details.

Findings

The results of the taken questionnaire (Appendix A) and tests (shown on the below graph) clearly demonstrated their language proficiency level, learning styles, strengths and weaknesses in learning process, as well their purposes and goals.

1. According to the results of analysis, the goals of the learners are to achieve high proficiency level of English in order to exploit it in their future careers, as some of them wish to be English teachers, others want to open their own English courses in their region or would like to pursue the MA degree in this major.
2. The findings of students' learning styles are shown on the bar chart below.

(The students passed www.whatismylearningstyle.com)

According to this chart we can see that the most of students are visual learners, which means they learn better if lessons are conducted with visual aids. It is necessary, of course, to take into account other types of learners. Therefore, I concluded that in the learning process the teacher should have individual approach toward each student.

3. The test results (passed on www.efset.org) of the level of language proficiency of students are represented in the pie chart below.

The test is recommended to quickly assess English skills both reading and listening. The following percentage determines proficiency level of English: 30%-60% - Beginner (meeting the demand of A1-A2 level); 60%-90% - Intermediate (B1-B2); 90%-100% - Advanced (C1-C2). According to the results only 3 students out of 10 got B1 level, others had A1 or A2 levels. From the pie chart it becomes obvious that the most of learners do not meet the requirements of this university’s curriculum. In accordance with the requirements of Common European Framework of References, which is used for the basis of curriculum, the second year students must have B1 level. If we take into consideration that the students’ level must correspond to B2 at the end of year, then it causes much more difficulties to them to achieve their goals.

4. The learning skills of students also significantly vary from each other. The outcomes of my analysis (reflects the students’ answers to specially prepared questionnaire) prove that students have different challenging areas in learning process as demonstrated on the bar graph below.

It leads to the finding that the students need definitely more training in writing skills. Their teacher also has the same opinion about the necessity of students’ training in this area. As she said most of the students’ level does not meet the requirements of B1level. That is why she asks them to work with extra textbooks on the top of the university recommended ones that would at the end help students to improve their knowledge and to bridge the gap in this specific area.

5. During my needs’ analysis I focused on one student, whose skills were proved to be higher with respect to the other students. This fact brought to my attention and I interviewed her in person. During the conversation I found out that besides going to specialized English school she worked with tutor for about one year in order to prepare for the entrance exams to the university. Her systematic work in improving her knowledge for the last several years helped her to get higher scores in the proficiency language test among her classmates. The goal of this learner is to improve writing and speaking skills for her future carrier. As in the perspectives she wants to work at one of the international organization, she would like to master especially these two skills, which request from her a lot of efforts nowadays. Key findings of the test results showed that she has a visual learning style (see attached Appendix B) and level B1 (Appendix C) according to requirements of Common European Framework of References.

In order to achieve the goal she follows some strategies in writing module such as note taking and peer working. As for her personal characteristics, she is a responsible and curious that may help her to reach the goals sooner, will she devise some more strategies and increase her motivation. My suggestions to improve her writing skills were to keep practice more and read a lot, as writing proficiency comes with practicing it and reading different books. In addition, as she is a visual learner I advise her to organize graphics to see her ideas or try to use brainstorming map to understand key features of her writing. This approach originates from a view of Schumaker J.B and Deshle D.D (1992), who advocate that learning strategy helps “to learn content or accomplish other tasks more effectively and efficiently”.

Conclusion

According to the analysis, it became clear that the students’ proficiency level of the observed group does not meet the requirements of the university curriculum. It seems like there is too much expecting from the second year students, as at the end of the year they must get B2 level according to the set of curriculum. In my opinion, the requirements of curriculum need to be revised and made suitable for learners’ needs. It would be appropriate for the learners to achieve B1 level instead of B2 in the second year of educational process.

I think that in order to achieve high language proficiency level, it would be applicable if lessons conducted with several interactive activities as students mentioned it in the survey. Moreover, the course book should be chosen appropriately in accordance with learners’ needs.

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